

Robust precoding weights for downlink D-MIMO in 6G Communications

Ke Wang Helmersson
Ericsson Research
Linköping, Sweden
ke@helmersson.one

Pål Frenger
Ericsson Research
Linköping, Sweden
pal.frenger@ericsson.com

Anders Helmersson
Linköping University
Linköping, Sweden
anders.helmersson@liu.se

Abstract—Point-to-point MIMO and massive MIMO techniques have played significant roles in the success of 4G and 5G radio networks, and in 6G we believe that distributed MIMO will play a similar critical role. The performance of downlink phase coherent distributed MIMO transmission relies on tight phase alignment between the serving access points (APs) in the system. In realistic scenarios, there will always be some level of phase misalignment between APs due to e.g., differences in the local clocks of the APs, which can severely degrade the performance.

One main contribution of this paper is that we propose the use of a Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) based solution for calculating downlink precoding weights in D-MIMO systems. The optimal LQR based precoding solution is numerically stable and computationally efficient, and it can easily utilise parallel computing in distributed or centralised hardware processors. Furthermore, we also show how the LQR based solution can be modified to include differently sized subsets of serving APs for each UE, which enables a scalable tradeoff between performance and complexity.

Another main contribution of the paper is that we identify a new phase misalignment problem in D-MIMO. The proposed LQR-based precoding method is the first solution that takes not only the channel estimation phase errors, but also the relative phase errors between serving APs into account when designing the downlink D-MIMO transmission precoder. By this, some of the performance lost due to different causes of phase misalignment can be regained. In the scenarios studied in this paper we observe 20-70% performance increase of the proposed method compared to a reference case where residual phase errors are ignored when determining the downlink precoding weights.

Index Terms—Distributed MIMO, downlink robust precoder, phase misalignment, Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR), Kalman filter, decentralised processing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Distributed MIMO (D-MIMO, also known as "cell-free massive MIMO", Radio Stripes [1], RadioWeaves [2], etc.) is a key technology candidate for the 6G physical layer. The basic idea is to distribute service antennas geographically and have them operate phase-coherently together [3].

In a typical D-MIMO deployment multiple access points (APs) are interconnected and configured in such a way that more than one AP can cooperate in coherent decoding of data from a given UE, and more than one AP can cooperate in coherent transmission of data to a UE. Each AP in turn may comprise multiple antenna elements that are configured to operate phase-coherently together. The preferred way of operation in a D-MIMO system is time-division duplexing (TDD),

relying on reciprocity of the propagation channel, whereby uplink pilots transmitted by the UEs are used to obtain both the uplink and downlink channel responses simultaneously. Various research projects, for example H2020-REINDEER [2], are addressing aspects relating to this architecture, including the design of beam-forming methods, random access signalling and procedures, etc. The phase misalignment problem has been discussed since massive MIMO was introduced in 5G. There are many solutions to calibrate and take the phase errors into account when designing the transmission precoders, see e.g., [4] and [5]. The phase misalignment considered in those precoders are caused by the channel estimation phase errors, due to e.g., timing differences in channels from different antennas, we call this the absolute phase error. With the introduction of D-MIMO, the antennas are no-longer co-located but rather geographically distributed. Besides the absolute phase errors, there are relative phase errors from antennas at different APs that are received at the receiver. The relative phase error causes phase misalignment between transmissions from different APs, which requires different procedures for calibration, see e.g. [6]. However, even after phase alignment there will be residual phase errors that cannot be compensated for, due to e.g., noisy calibration measurements, tiny movements of antennas at different APs caused by e.g., temperature and wind in environment. Different from the known topic on phase misalignment caused by the absolute phase errors the phase misalignment identified in this paper is caused by the residual phase errors which hasn't been included in the calculation of precoding weights earlier.

The paper is organised as follows: We introduce a downlink D-MIMO network in Section II. A brief description of centralised and decentralised precoding methods from the literature is provided in Section III. The proposed LQR precoding method is described in Section IV. In Section V we extend the LQR formulation to also include a model of the phase misalignment errors between APs, with the intention of enabling a more robust performance in the presence of residual phase errors in the D-MIMO network. Additional per-antenna element or per-AP power control is discussed in Section VI. The numerical verifications of the robust LQR based precoding calculation method and comparison with other published methods are provided in Section VII. Finally, the paper is concluded in Section VIII.

II. D-MIMO NETWORK

A D-MIMO network, see Fig. 1, consists of L geographically distributed APs, each equipped with N antenna elements. The total number of antennas in the network is $N \times L$. The APs are connected via front-haul links to one or more CPUs (Central Processing Units), which facilitate the coordination among APs. Note that the front-haul links between the APs and the CPU can be serial or parallel connections, as well as wired or wireless. The APs are cooperating to jointly serve K UEs (User Equipments) in the coverage area by phase coherent transmission in the downlink and phase coherent reception in the uplink.

In the downlink, as shown in Fig. 1, the data symbol s_k to UE_k is transmitted from the CPU via a number of APs, AP_1, \dots, AP_L . The transmitted signal from AP_l towards UE_k use the precoding weights $\mathbf{w}_{l,k}$, which are calculated based on channel state information derived from uplink pilots. Note that the precoding vector is not assumed to have unit norm, i.e. $\mathbf{w}_{l,k}$, can equivalently be expressed as an amplitude $\sqrt{\rho_{l,k}}$ multiplied with a precoding vector $\mathbf{v}_{l,k}$ with unit norm (i.e. $\mathbf{w}_{l,k} = \sqrt{\rho_{l,k}}\mathbf{v}_{l,k}$, where $\|\mathbf{v}_{l,k}\|^2 = 1$ and consequently $\|\mathbf{w}_{l,k}\|^2 = \rho_{l,k}$).

In the ideal case the precoding vectors are designed so that signals from different APs are coherently and constructively combined at the desired receiver antenna, UE_k as shown in Fig. 1, and destructively combined (cancelled out) at interfered receivers, $UE_{k'}$ as shown in Fig. 1. UEs at other locations receive signals from different APs that add up non-coherently (i.e. with random phase).

In Fig. 1 we also introduce some of the notation that will be used throughout this paper: The downlink channel between UE_k and AP_l and is denoted $\mathbf{b}_{l,k}$ and in case the UE has a single antenna element this is a row vector of size N . The receiver noise at UE_k is denoted n_k , which is a scalar value in case the UE has a single antenna element. In this paper we will use $\mathbf{h}_{l,k}$ to denote the uplink channel and $\mathbf{b}_{l,k}$ to denote the downlink channel. The uplink and downlink channel estimates are denoted $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{l,k}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_{l,k}$, respectively. If the uplink channel and downlink channel are reciprocal, then we know that $\mathbf{b}_{l,k} = \mathbf{h}_{l,k}^H$ and consequently $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_{l,k} = \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{l,k}^H$. The signal received at each UE is a weighted sum of transmitted signals from the serving APs. This signal will consist of both the desired signal, the interference from all other transmissions (in the example in Fig. 1 we only included the desired signal), and receiver noise. If all L APs are serving UE_k we can write the received signal as

$$y_k = \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{b}_{l,k} \mathbf{u}_l + n_k, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{b}_{l,k}$ is the downlink channel from AP_l to UE_k , and n_k is the receiver noise at UE_k .

III. EXISTING DOWNLINK D-MIMO PRECODING METHODS

In [7] several centralised and decentralised downlink precoding methods using MMSE were proposed and evaluated.

Fig. 1: Downlink data transmission in D-MIMO network.

For reference, we summarise these methods briefly in this section, more details are found in [7]. Minimum mean square error (MMSE) precoding (see [7]) can be obtained using

$$\bar{\mathbf{w}}_k^{\text{MMSE}} = p_k \left(\sum_{i=1}^K p_i \mathbf{D}_k (\hat{\mathbf{h}}_i \hat{\mathbf{h}}_i^H + \mathbf{C}_i) \mathbf{D}_k + \sigma_{UL}^2 \mathbf{I}_{NL} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{D}_k \hat{\mathbf{h}}_k \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_i$ is the uplink channel estimation for UE_i , $i = 1, \dots, K$; $p_i : i = 1, \dots, K$ is the transmit power assigned to UEs from all serving APs. The matrix \mathbf{D}_i is a block-diagonal matrix indicating which APs that are transmitting to UE_i ; and σ_{UL} is the standard deviation of the receiver noise. This centralised MMSE precoding method is optimal in terms of minimising a sum of mean-square errors. However the computational complexity is high since it requires first an inverse of an $NL \times NL$ matrix and then a matrix-vector multiplication. In this paper we will refer to this method as C-ALL, which stands for "a centralised method that uses all APs in the entire D-MIMO network".

Beside the C-ALL method, we also compare with other less-complex precoding schemes proposed by [7]. For example, the Dynamic Cooperation Cluster (DCC) method applies the orthogonal pilots assignment from a master AP where surrounding APs are invited to form UE clusters (see Algorithm 4.1 in [7] for more details). Another reduced complexity method for calculating precoder is denoted partial MMSE (P-MMSE) in [7] where only the UEs that are partially served by the same APs as UE_k are included in the precoder calculation, i.e. the UEs have indices in the set

$$\mathcal{S}_k = \{i : \mathbf{D}_k \mathbf{D}_i \neq \mathbf{0}_{NL \times NL}\}. \quad (3)$$

By utilizing \mathcal{S}_k , P-MMSE precoding can be calculated as

$$\bar{\mathbf{w}}_k^{\text{P-MMSE}} = p_k \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_k} p_i \mathbf{D}_k \hat{\mathbf{h}}_i \hat{\mathbf{h}}_i^H \mathbf{D}_k + \mathbf{Z}_{\mathcal{S}_k} + \sigma_{UL}^2 \mathbf{I}_{LN} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{D}_k \hat{\mathbf{h}}_k \quad (4)$$

with

$$\mathbf{Z}_{\mathcal{S}_k} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_k} p_i \mathbf{D}_k \mathbf{C}_i \mathbf{D}_k, \quad (5)$$

where the matrix \mathbf{C}_i is the error correlation matrix of the channel \mathbf{h}_i . The P-MMSE scheme is not optimal, but it reduces the inverse of an $NL \times NL$ matrix to the inverse of an $N|\mathcal{M}_k| \times N|\mathcal{M}_k|$ matrix where \mathcal{M}_k consists of the indexes of APs serving UE_k . P-MMSE can also be used together with the DCC scheme, which is denoted as P-DCC in this paper.

Furthermore, all of the above methods can be modified to use only information that is locally available in each APs to calculate the precoding weights. For reference, we also evaluate these methods in the numerical section of this paper. They are denoted L-ALL, L-DCC and LP-DCC, where the L denotes "local" (see [7] for further details).

IV. THE PROPOSED LQR-BASED D-MIMO DOWNLINK PRECODING METHOD

The existing precoding methods [7] do not consider any phase errors between different APs, but rather assume the perfect phase alignment. In all realistic scenarios, there will be some level of phase misalignment between APs. In a D-MIMO network with multiple serving APs, different APs cannot transmit at exactly the same time, i.e. with the same phase, hence there is a phase misalignment at the receive side when UEs are served by several serving APs. This problem is also described in [6]. We propose in this section a new method to design the D-MIMO downlink precoder which takes the phase misalignment between APs into account. The downlink precoding can be considered as the counterparts of the uplink combining. In [8] we introduced the use of Kalman filters for uplink combining in a D-MIMO network. Using the duality principle in optimisation theory, the dual problem of the Kalman filtering is known as the linear quadratic regulator (LQR) problem [9]. We introduce in this section how to calculate the downlink precoding weights by using the optimal LQR solution, which is a new way to design the downlink transmission precoder by taking the phase misalignment into account.

To enable formulating of the downlink precoder calculations as a LQR problem, we express the downlink signals to all K UEs as the vector $\mathbf{s} = [s_1 \dots s_K]^T$, ($\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{C}^K$). This vector of data symbols is to be transmitted from the CPU to the UEs via a subset of the serving APs in the D-MIMO network. To simplify the analysis, we will assume that the data symbols are normally distributed complex random variables with zero mean and variance 1. In case they are selected from a QAM signal constellation this assumption is still a good approximation.

Since each AP has N antenna elements the transmitted signal from AP $_l$, denoted as \mathbf{u}_l , is a vector of length N . The precoding weight matrix containing the precoding weight vectors for each UE as columns, is written as $\mathbf{W}_l = [\mathbf{w}_{l,1} \dots \mathbf{w}_{l,K}]$. The size \mathbf{W}_l is $N \times K$, and $\mathbf{W}_l \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}$.

In [10] a decentralised subset method is proposed, where instead of assigning all L APs as serving APs, a subset of APs is selected (based on e.g path-gain), to serve each UE. We denote the subset by sub- ℓ when ℓ out of L APs are selected. The minimum subset, sub-1, can be selected based on the best path gain for each UE. The maximum subset, sub- L , consists of all APs that connected to the same CPU. Let \mathcal{L} be the subset of consisting of ℓ serving APs for the UE $_k$, $\mathcal{L} \subset \{1, \dots, L\}$, then the received signal can be written as

$$y_k = \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}} \mathbf{b}_{l,k} \mathbf{u}_l + n_k. \quad (6)$$

To simplify these expressions further we define a channel matrix and signal vector for all serving APs as

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{b}_K \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{u}_L \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{b}_k = [\mathbf{b}_{1,k} \dots \mathbf{b}_{L,k}]$. \mathbf{B} has a size $K \times NL$. We further define a receiver noise vector as $\mathbf{n} = [n_1 \dots n_K]^T$, which gives us

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{n}, \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{y} is the vector of received signals for all UE $_k$, $k = 1, \dots, K$, i.e. $\mathbf{y} = [y_1 \dots y_K]^T$.

Proposition 1: The downlink precoding weights for all UEs from all antennas can be calculated by minimising the following linear quadratic expression:

$$\mathbb{E} \{ (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{s})^H \mathbf{P} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{s}) + \mathbf{u}^H \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{u} \}, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{P} and $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ are weighting matrices. The linear quadratic function (9) is called the LQR cost function.

Proof: Considering the case that all APs are the serving APs for UEs. Let $\mathbf{W}^T = [\mathbf{W}_1 \dots \mathbf{W}_L]$ be the matrix containing all precoding weights for all APs. Since $\mathbf{u}_l = \mathbf{W}_l \mathbf{s}$, and $\mathbf{W}_l = [\mathbf{w}_{l,1} \dots \mathbf{w}_{l,K}]$, we have

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{s}. \quad (10)$$

The LQR problem is to find \mathbf{u} given the signal \mathbf{s} so that the LQR cost function is minimised for the given weighting matrices \mathbf{P} and $\mathbf{\Sigma}$. The optimal solution to the LQR problem is given by, see [9] for more details,

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{P}, \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{R} is the covariance matrix

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{P} \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{\Sigma}^2. \quad (12)$$

Using the solution (11) as the precoding weight matrix \mathbf{W} on the data signals \mathbf{s} , the transmitting signals \mathbf{u} can be calculated by (10). Since $\mathbf{W}^T = [\mathbf{W}_1 \dots \mathbf{W}_L]$ and each $\mathbf{W}_l = [\mathbf{w}_{l,1} \dots \mathbf{w}_{l,K}]$, contains the precoding weights $\mathbf{w}_{l,k}$ to be used by AP $_l$ as precoding weights to send the data signal to UE $_k$ where $l = 1, \dots, L$ and $k = 1, \dots, K$. The precoding weights obtained in this way is optimal in terms of minimising the LQR cost function (9) according to the well-known Optimization Theory in [9]. ■

Remark 1: The weighting matrices \mathbf{P} and $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ can be used to prioritise minimisation of the error for individual UEs and the power for individual antenna elements as discussed in Section VI.

Remark 2: As an example, to explain the sizes of matrices in (12), considering L serving APs, $\mathbf{W}^T = [\mathbf{W}_1 \dots \mathbf{W}_L]$ is of size $NL \times K$; the channel matrix \mathbf{B} is of size $K \times NL$, and hence \mathbf{B}^H is of size $NL \times K$; \mathbf{P} is of size $K \times K$ and $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is of size $NL \times NL$, and thus the covariance matrix \mathbf{R} is of size $NL \times NL$.

Remark 3: If downlink and uplink are reciprocal, $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{H}^H$, the duality of the LQR downlink precoding is the uplink

Kalman filtering. The uplink combining weights are given by the Kalman filter gain. The Kalman filter gain at AP_{*l*} is given by $\mathcal{K} = \mathbf{P}_0 \mathbf{H}_l^H (\mathbf{H}_l \mathbf{P}_0 \mathbf{H}_l^H + \mathbf{R}_l)^{-1}$, see [8] for more details.

The implementation complexity of minimising the LQR expressions is dominated by the calculation of the inverse of the covariance matrix \mathbf{R} . The more serving APs in the subset the larger the size of the covariance matrix becomes. The implementation complexity was analysed in [8] where the Kalman filter was proposed for uplink combining. Since LQR is the dual of the Kalman filter, the complexity analysis in [8] is valid for solving LQR as well. Here we also propose, as in [8], to use the square-root implementation for solving the LQR problem as it is shown to be numerically stable when inverting the covariance matrix.

Another advantage of using the above LQR expression to determine precoding weights is that the processing can be decentralised and/or performed in parallel for each subset of APs. The subset size can be adjusted to trade-off computational complexity and performance. We formulate the LQR solution of a subset of serving APs as:

Corollary 1: The LQR optimal solution can be applied to calculate the precoding weights for any number of serving APs in a subset sub- ℓ .

Proof: Let sub- ℓ consists of ℓ serving APs, $\{\text{AP}_{l_1}, \text{AP}_{l_2}, \dots, \text{AP}_{l_\ell}\}$ for UE_{*k*}. Replacing the channel matrix \mathbf{B} by using $\mathbf{b}_k = [\mathbf{b}_{l_1,k} \dots \mathbf{b}_{l_\ell,k}]$ in (8) and the received signal by (6). The LQR optimal solution described by *Proposition 1* can be applied to sub- ℓ and provides the precoding weight matrix \mathbf{W} as $\mathbf{W}^T = [\mathbf{W}_{l_1} \dots \mathbf{W}_{l_\ell}]$. This precoding matrix \mathbf{W} has a size $N\ell \times K$. The sizes of other involved matrices described in *Remark 2* can be obtained by replacing L with ℓ . ■

Remark 4: The LQR optimal solution is equivalent to the optimal solution of minimum mean-square error (MMSE). The dual problem of the LQR is the Kalman Filter. In [8] we show that the performance measure in terms of SINR for each UE is equivalent to the inverse of the covariance matrix given by the Kalman filter. Hence minimising the LQR cost function results in the best SINR under the assumption of duality.

V. D-MIMO DOWNLINK PRECODING WEIGHTS THAT ARE ROBUST TO PHASE MISALIGNED APs

In Section IV we assume that the phase alignment between transmitting APs is ideal. In real scenarios where D-MIMO network is deployed, there will always be some timing differences between APs when signals arrive at UE receiver since the antennas are distributed. These timing differences result in the relative phase errors when the signals reach the intended receiver. Hence there is a need to calibrate the phases of antennas at APs using some synchronisation procedure to achieve coherent phase addition and suppression of interference at the UE antenna. However, even after phase calibration there will be phase misalignment caused by the residual phase errors that cannot be compensated for, due to e.g., noisy calibration measurements, tiny movements of antennas at different APs caused by e.g., temperature and wind in

environment and movements of UEs. There will always remain a phase uncertainty after synchronisation and calibration. Even though we don't know the magnitude of residual phase errors, we cannot ignore the existence of these errors when design the optimal precoders. We propose to model the residual phase errors by defining an effective downlink channel, including phase misalignment errors, for all UEs as

$$\mathbf{B}^{\text{eff}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_1^{\text{eff}} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{b}_K^{\text{eff}} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{where } \mathbf{b}_k^{\text{eff}} = [e^{j\varphi_1} \mathbf{b}_{1,k} \dots e^{j\varphi_L} \mathbf{b}_{L,k}]. \quad (13)$$

The effective channel can also be written as $\mathbf{B}^{\text{eff}} = \widehat{\mathbf{B}} + \Delta_{\text{tot}} \in \mathcal{N}(\widehat{\mathbf{B}}, \mathbf{C}_{\text{tot}})$ with mean $\widehat{\mathbf{B}}$ and covariance \mathbf{C}_{tot} . Note that $\Delta_{\text{tot}} = \mathbf{B}^{\text{eff}} - \widehat{\mathbf{B}}$ and hence $\Delta_{\text{tot}} \in \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{C}_{\text{tot}})$ where $\mathbf{C}_{\text{tot}} = \mathbf{C}_{\text{ch}} + (1 - e^{-\sigma^2}) \widehat{\mathbf{B}}^H \widehat{\mathbf{B}}$ and \mathbf{C}_{ch} is the covariance matrix of the channel estimation error, which includes the absolute phase errors, and σ is the standard deviation of the relative phase errors.

Proposition 2: Precoding weights, which is more robust to both absolute and relative phase errors, are obtained by modifying the LQR expression to include a model of the residual phase errors as

$$\mathbb{E} \left\{ \left((\widehat{\mathbf{B}} + \Delta_{\text{tot}}) \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{s} \right)^H \mathbf{P} \left((\widehat{\mathbf{B}} + \Delta_{\text{tot}}) \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{s} \right) + \mathbf{u}^H \Sigma \mathbf{u} \right\}. \quad (14)$$

Proof: Calculating the LQR optimal solution by minimising this cost function (14). The optimal solution is

$$\mathbf{u} = \widetilde{\mathbf{W}} \mathbf{s}, \quad (15)$$

where $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}$ is the robust downlink precoding weight matrix which can be expressed as

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{W}} = \widetilde{\mathbf{R}}^{-1} \widehat{\mathbf{B}}^H \mathbf{P}, \quad (16)$$

and the total uncertainty Δ_{tot} is included in the covariance matrix $\widetilde{\mathbf{R}}$ as

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{R}} = \widehat{\mathbf{B}}^H \widehat{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{P} + \mathbb{E} \{ \Delta_{\text{tot}}^H \mathbf{P} \Delta_{\text{tot}} \} + \Sigma^2. \quad (17)$$

The phase misalignment uncertainty is considered as a part of total uncertainty which is given by $\mathbb{E} \{ \Delta_{\text{tot}}^H \mathbf{P} \Delta_{\text{tot}} \} = \sum_k p_{k,k} \mathbf{C}_{k,k}$ and $\mathbf{C}_{k,k}$ are diagonal elements of the channel covariance \mathbf{C}_{tot} and $p_{k,k}$ are the diagonal elements of weighting matrix \mathbf{P} . In this way the phase misalignment uncertainty is included in the covariance matrix when LQR minimises the cost function (14). The LQR optimal solution (15) provides the precoding weights $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}$ which is robust to not only the absolute phase errors but also the relative phase errors. ■

VI. ADDITIONAL POWER CONTROL PER ANTENNA OR AP

The precoding weights calculated based on the optimal solution of the LQR cost function, (9) or (14), minimises not only the estimation error but also the transmission power. After the optimal precoding weights are obtained, there is usually no need to perform any additional power control as suggested in e.g. [7]. The optimal transmission amplitude is simply the Euclidian norm of the precoding weight. Any

Fig. 2: Path-gain in a D-MIMO network with 36 APs (using parameters from Table I).

additional power control would only destroy the optimisation that balances the distribution of transmission power among the antenna elements. However, if some transmission power exceed the maximum power budget of an antenna element or the total available power at APs, some additional power scaling is required.

One simple way is to scale down the weights by a constant ρ equally for all antenna elements, and in this way the relative balance of the transmission power given by the optimal precoding weights is maintained. This power scaling method works fine whenever the power scaling factor required is close to 1 (i.e. for minor adjustments). In case larger power scaling adjustments are required, we can instead adjust the weighting matrix, \mathbf{P} or Σ , in the LQR cost function to penalise the power of the antenna element individually before minimising the LQR expression (9) or (14), and thereby obtain precoding weights that are all within the power budget of the antennas and APs.

VII. NUMERICAL COMPARISON

We evaluate the performance of different precoding methods using simulations where the established methods described in [7] are used as benchmarks. To be able to compare the work done in [7] and our LQR based solution, we used the same channel propagation model as [7] where a matlab based simulator was provided. A summary of simulation parameters is given in Table I. We use a grid deployment of 36 APs, that are deployed in a $100 \times 100 \text{ m}^2$ area. The path gain for different positions in the deployment area is illustrated in Fig. 2. Each AP has $N = 4$ antenna elements and $K = 20$ UEs are randomly generated in the area.

The performance metrics used for comparing different precoding methods is the achievable Spectral Efficiency (SE) [bit/s/Hz]. For the reference cases defined in III, the simulations are based on the Matlab code provided by [7]. For the *LQR based precoding methods*, the square-root implementation using duality of the Kalman filter as described by Remark 4 in Section IV. Each simulation contains 1000 random channel realisations and 8000 random UEs samples.

TABLE I: SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Carrier frequency	2 GHz
Bandwidth	20 MHz
Duplex	Symmetric TDD Number of data samples for UL and DL $\tau_D = \tau_C - \tau_P$
Simulation area	$100 \times 100 \text{ m}^2$
Wrap-around	8 twin areas
Channel Assumptions	Perfect reciprocity, Block fading, Independent Rayleigh fading Correlated log-normal shadow fading, $\sigma_{sh} = 4\text{dB}$, 9 m correlation distance 3GPP Urban Microcell path-loss model
Coherence time	$\tau_C = 200$ samples
Channel estimation	τ_P uplink pilots (no downlink pilots), random pilot allocation
UE, AP height	1.5 m and 10 m respectively
UE and AP power	100 mW
Antenna power budget	50 mW (4 antenna elements per AP)
Noise power	-94 dBm

The impact of phase misalignment on the D-MIMO performance is shown in Fig. 3. In this figure we show different precoding methods on the x-axis and the 10th percentile of the UE spectral efficiency (SE) on the y-axis. The first four precoding methods from the left are benchmark methods including centralised methods (C-All, P-DCC) and decentralised methods (L-All, LP-DCC), see Section III for details. The precoder calculation methods based on the proposed LQR minimisation are denoted by $\text{sub}\ell$, where $\ell = 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32$, or 36.

We show two groups of simulation results in Fig. 3. The group with solid curves are the references where the transmission precoding weights are designed without considering the existence of residual phase errors (see Section IV). The group with dashed curves are results based on the proposed robust LQR method where both absolute phase errors and residual phase errors are included in the design of transmission precoding weights (see Section V).

Fig. 3: The performance with and without robust precoding weights.

The problem of phase misalignment caused by residual phase errors exists in the non-ideal cases. However, the magnitude of residual phase errors are unknown and random. In our evaluations we model the residual phase error φ as

a random process with a zero-mean Gaussian distribution $\varphi \in \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$, where σ is the standard deviation. For a real system the standard deviation can be estimated using a test mobile when the D-MIMO system is deployed. In the simulations we varied the standard deviation σ from 1° to 45° . In this simulation setup, the weighting matrices used by the LQR cost function, \mathbf{P} and $\mathbf{\Sigma}$, have the same values on the diagonal elements, $p_{kk} = 100$ for weighting matrix \mathbf{P} and square-root of noise power for weighting matrix $\mathbf{\Sigma}$. The solid blue curve on the top in Fig. 3, $\sigma = 0$, represents an ideal case with perfect phase alignment between APs. We can see that the performance degrades when the standard deviation of phase error increases. We also see that the "sub1" case is not impacted by phase misalignment errors between APs (for obvious reasons). For $\sigma \leq 16^\circ$ a minor performance degradation is observed for "sub2", i.e. only two serving APs for each UE, while for larger subsets ("sub4", "sub8", "sub16", "sub32", "sub36"), more than two serving APs, the performance degradations are significant. We can also see that the more serving APs the larger impact of phase errors. In the case when $\sigma \geq 45^\circ$, the D-MIMO gains vanish when more APs are added, and the "sub1" (single AP serving each UE) becomes the best choice. To achieve D-MIMO gain by using larger subsets robust precoding weights are needed to reduce the impact of phase misalignment errors. We show in Fig. 3 a second group of simulation results with dashed curves where the robust precoding weights using the method proposed in *Proposition 2* were applied. Note that the robust LQR solution applies only to the "subset methods", not the existing MMSE methods given by [7]. We can see that the performance gains are in the range of 20% to 70% compared to the reference results (solid curves of same colour). Although we don't regain all performance lost due to phase misalignment errors, the gain with the proposed robust LQR-based precoding method is still significant in many cases.

Fig. 4: Gains using robust LQR precoding weights.

In Fig. 4 we show the percentage gain of the robust precoding method on the y-axis, increasing standard deviation of phase misalignment from σ from 1° to 45° on the x-axis. The number of serving APs for each UE are shown in bars in different colours. The relative performance gain using robust LQR method is depended on the number of serving APs and

the phase misalignment errors.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Designing high performing, low complexity, and robust algorithms for coherent D-MIMO is of great importance for 6G. This paper identified a new phase misalignment problem and proposed a new solution using linear quadratic regulator (LQR) to determine the downlink precoding weights in a D-MIMO network. The paper could be the first one to present a solution that takes the residual phase errors into account in D-MIMO systems, and providing a starting point for designing downlink transmission precoders that are robust to phase misalignment errors.

The proposed LQR based method provides an optimal solution by minimising a weighted combination of the estimation error of the signal received by the UE and the transmission power of APs. The LQR based method can be applied for one serving AP or multiple serving APs, which enables scalable trade-offs between computational complexity and performance.

From implementation point of view, the proposed LQR method can apply the square-root implementation which is shown to be numerically sound when inverting the covariance matrix. The proposed LQR precoding method is further made more robust by including a model of the residual phase errors, and the gain by using the robust LQR optimal solution is in the range of 20% to 70% in the simulated scenarios.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has received funding from the REINDEER project of the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101013425.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Interdonato, E. Björnson, H. Q. Ngo, P. Frenger, and E. G. Larsson, "Ubiquitous cell-free massive MIMO," *EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, vol. 2019:197, 2019.
- [2] REINDEER-Horizon-2020, "Deliverable D3.1: Analytical performance metrics and physical-layer solutions," 26 January, 2022.
- [3] E. Björnson and L. Sanguinetti, "Making cell-free massive MIMO competitive with MMSE processing and centralized implementation," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 19, pp. 182–186, Jan. 2020.
- [4] R. Rogalin, O. Y. Bursalioglu, H. Papadopoulos, G. Caire, A. F. Molisch, A. Michaloliakos, V. Balan, and K. Psounis, "Scalable synchronization and reciprocity calibration for distributed multiuser MIMO," *IEEE transactions on wireless communications*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 1815–1831, 2014.
- [5] J. Vieira, F. Rusek, O. Edfors, S. Malkowsky, L. Liu, and F. Tufvesson, "Reciprocity calibration for massive MIMO: Proposal, modeling, and validation," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 3042–3056, 2017.
- [6] E. G. Larsson and J. Vieira, "Phase Calibration of Distributed Antenna Arrays," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, 2023.
- [7] Ö. T. Demir, E. Björnson, and L. Sanguinetti, *Foundations of User-Centric Cell-Free Massive MIMO*. PO Box 179, Delft, The Netherlands: now Publishers Inc., 2021.
- [8] K. W. Helmersson, P. Frenger, and A. Helmersson, "Uplink D-MIMO processing using Kalman filter Combining," in *Proc. IEEE Global Communications Conference*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, December 2022.
- [9] B. D. O. Anderson and J. B. Moore, *Optimal Control: Linear Quadratic Methods*. Dover Publication Inc., 2007.
- [10] K. W. Helmersson, P. Frenger, and A. Helmersson, "Uplink D-MIMO with decentralized subset combining," in *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Communications*, Seoul, South Korea, May 2022.